

CHANGES IN THE LIVER OF RABBITS IN THE DEFICIENCY OF THE TRACE ELEMENT COBALT

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ABSTRACT: *in this study, the lack of Co in the body was studied in rabbits. For this, a change in the composition of the liver of the internal organ of rabbits was observed.*

Keywords: *cobalt, Saturn, spectrometry, Mufel oven.*

Relevance of the topic: lack of microelements in the long term and the effect of ionizing radiation on the body primarily negatively affect the metabolism of minerals and vitamins, causing a deterioration in the functional state of the liver, kidneys and thyroid gland, as well as a decrease in the functional activity of immuno - complement cells and organs. {3,9,10,11,13,}

The main purpose of the work: to identify changes that occur in the lack of Co in lactating animals (rabbits of mixed breed).

Material and methods the body weight of the mixed breed is the same 2500gr male sex age is the same for conducting research experiments-a 4-month , clinically healthy 100nafar healthy rabbit was selected . as the first group for the experiment, 70 of the second group30 were allocated for the quality of the control group. {24,23,20} The experiment was carried out in SamTI vivari during the 6oy from April to November..Experimental rabbits were fed with Co low-catching products. Rabbits in the control group were raised according to the usual diet. After 6 months, the internal organs of the animals were separated and examined. In this experiment, trace elements were detected in the “Saturn “ spectrophotometer in the form of an atomic adsorption method. To do this , take 5gr from each organ and burn it until the 1800C dryer is completely darkened in the closet. Then the experiment is carried out on the Mufel heater. And heated at 4500 C until Ash is formed . To speed up the burning process , a few drops of nitric acid are dripped into ready-made samples mixed with 0.1 gr of HCL kilotage and brought to a solution state .The liquid substance is transferred to an atomic state, after which the Co element in the process of radiation is sufficient and insufficient compared to the Meyor .{1,2,6,8,12} statistical calculations were carried out in the Exel program.

DISCUSSION: According to the characteristic signs of Co deficiency in rabbits manifested in 2 groups: strong weight loss, which is observed as osteotystrophy, ishtax. The first group is accompanied by a decrease in body Vaz on average in 14 rabbits-20% : In the second group, the body weight did not change but the symptoms of mild poisoning –the lack of appetite being low signs of vomiting wool snoring signs such as being gujanak were observed in 56 rabbits (80 %) during this time, the weight of rabbits in the control group increased to 300-500 their Active Mobility no negative changes were observed in the When the liver tissue of rabbits was specteriametry, the amount of its element in the liver was in the experimental group and amounted to 0.526-0.479 mg/kg. The comparative studied control group was found to be 0.0766-0.0658 mg/kg in rabbit liver. {15,14,17,19,}

CONCLUSION, chronic Co deficiency leads to a decrease in appetite to a decrease in physiological paralysis in the body to the manifestation of symptoms characteristic of general intoxication, as a result of which vomiting occurs due to wool snoring, vomiting, unchanged or decreased body Vaz, in their liver spectrometry, the amount of Co was determined to be 0.02 mg/kg lower than in

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